

THE STRUCTURE OF THE STRATEGIC GOAL OF THE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract: The development of the strategy of the educational institution is carried out in an environment of uncertainty, which causes processes both outside and inside the organization. The external environment is characterized by the instability of factors that force the educational institution to change. In this thesis we are talk about the development of the strategy of the educational institution.

Key words: Innovation, pedagogical technology, management system, Strategy implementation, management of the educational system, strategic plan.

Developing a strategy involves answering three important questions:

What is the current state of the educational institution?

Where do you want to be in three, five, ten years?

How to achieve the desired result?

To answer the first question, before deciding where to go next, it is important to have a good understanding of the current situation where the PO is located. For this, an information base is needed to ensure the adoption process. relevant information for analyzing past, present and future situations for strategic decisions. The second question reflects an important feature of the strategic development of the educational institution, its orientation to the future. To answer this, it is necessary to clearly define what to strive for, what goals to set. The third issue is related to the implementation of the chosen strategy, during which the previous two steps can be adjusted. The most important components or constraints at this stage are the existing or existing resources, the management system, the organizational structure, and the personnel who will implement the chosen strategy.

The purpose of strategy development is to use the strengths of the educational institution, compensate for its weaknesses, and achieve a long-term competitive advantage, taking into account the advantages and threats created by the educational institution. external environment organizations. The most important factors for the success of an educational institution are the use of human resources and latent reserves. organizational culture.

Strategy implementation solves two interrelated tasks:

1. Market strategy management training services. Strategy is a means of changing the relations of the educational institution with partners and competitors, as a result of which the educational institution will have competitive advantages.

2. Management of the educational system: internal changes (a set of material and technical, methodological equipment of institutions, changes in the organizational structure and professional excellence of its leaders and employees). This allows you to respond appropriately to changes in the external environment, adapt to them and use them for your own purposes.

Strategy development begins with detailed answers to the following questions:

What is the educational system, educational institution and their activities today?

What are our services and products, tasks, place in the education market?

What should they be like tomorrow, in 5-10 years?

What do we need to do to achieve our goals?

When developing a strategy, it is necessary to take into account the multi-level nature of the activity of the educational institution. The city system of education related to the entire educational institution, taking into account the interests of the corporate level. The level of assortment determines the directions of activities for the implementation of educational services for all categories of consumers. The functional level ensures the solution of the tasks set in the previous levels.

When developing the strategy, the conditions around the educational system are analyzed:

Development possibilities and trends of budget and commercial demand for education system, educational institution services;

Possibilities of integration with other educational systems, educational institutions;

Opportunities for vertical integration of education with external developers, customers, intermediaries and consumers of services;

The state and prospects of the management system of the educational institution and the potential of personnel.

Strategy development is based on a number of principles that allow you to more clearly define the ways to achieve strategic goals.

The theory of gradual growth is the gradual adaptation of the system of the educational institution to the conditions of the external environment.

Flexible approach - rapid changes and planning activities based on current conditions.

Creativity- Emphasis on foresight in solving present and possible future problems.

Consider the following when developing a strategy:

Covering all areas of educational system, educational institution activity;

Compatibility with external conditions;

Compliance with resource capabilities;

Communication with the long-term directions of development of the educational system, educational institution;

Taking into account the priorities in the goals and tasks adopted by the educational institution;

The development strategy of the educational institution can be presented in the form of a strategic plan. A strategic plan is a short document focused on the main thing to increase the competitiveness of an educational institution. A strategic plan contains ideas for management and employees, potential investors, authorities and the public to guide them in making quick decisions, taking into account the vision of the future. The strategic plan does not cancel or replace other types of plans, it only defines development in the most important, priority directions for the educational institution. The strategic plan will be developed and implemented on the basis of an open, public-private partnership.

The strategic plan defines the general direction (strategy) of the development of the educational institution for up to 10 years. This is the main focus, the most promising directions, potential, strengths and weaknesses identified on the basis of the analysis of the educational institution, possible scenarios of the development of the outside world.

- the main goal of the development of the educational institution at the current stage;

The main strategic directions for achieving the main goal;

- goals within strategic directions;

Specific measures for the implementation of the selected strategies with the determination of indicators of implementation of planned activities, cost estimates, participants in the implementation of activities.

It is recommended to develop the text of the strategic plan (strategy) in three options:

The main official version;

The full version includes the detailed rationale of the chosen strategy, as well as the projects and programs that define the actions of the plan. It is released as a bundle of applications to the main version;

Presentation version describing the main positions of the main version.

The following main stages are carried out in the process of strategy development:

Analysis (state diagnosis, study of external and internal factors determining development, SWOT analysis);

Setting the goal (determining and confirming the main goal, main strategic directions, goals),

Planning (formulation of personal strategies and selection of measures to achieve goals in each direction, distribution of responsibility for the implementation of the plan).

Improvement and improvement of the strategic plan is carried out every 3-5 years.

The main task of strategy implementation is to build an organization with high strategic potential, able to quickly adapt to changes in the external environment, competitive and achieve consistent high results in the long term. In the process of implementing the strategy for the implementation of this task, the administration of the educational institution focuses its activities on the following areas:

Allocation of resources between activities, which is especially important when resources are scarce or at a high cost;

Policy support for strategy, including ensuring continuity of strategy elements at all levels of hierarchy and functional units by communicating, coordinating and harmonizing strategic visions, missions, goals and strategic guidelines throughout the faculty. Create. all plans, programs, projects of the educational institution;

motivation of teaching staff to strategic goals, including not only financial incentive methods, but also administrative methods of controlling and influencing employees, as well as measures to encourage morale and career growth encourage;

ensure fair remuneration, taking into account the level of responsibility for the achievement of results in the process of implementing strategic and tactical plans and the contribution to the achievement of the set strategic goals and objectives;

Creating a corporate culture that supports the implementation of the strategy, including "building the corporate spirit", developing employee loyalty, reducing staff turnover, increasing initiative in accordance with the goals of the educational institution, socializing the organization's employees;

Provide all employees of the educational institution with the necessary information and communications, develop methodological and organizational tools to manage the implementation of the strategy;

Use of positive experiences for the continuous development of the institution, including the establishment of a system of continuous professional development and professional development of pedagogic personnel, exchange of mutual experience, support of initiatives, permanent educational and practical seminars for the purpose of creating a creative environment organization; career management;

Implementation of direct strategic management, formation of a continuous strategic planning system, monitoring of strategic changes in the external and internal environment, continuity of strategic plans, programs, projects.

Responsibilities for strategy formation should be distributed taking into account the characteristics of the organization's culture, traditions and management style. A mismatch between culture and type of responsibility often results in ineffective strategy. Thus, if an authoritarian culture is formed in an educational institution where the leader's decision is final and non-negotiable, the introduction of the system of group responsibility actually paralyzes the institution's activities, because team members have equal rights. powers cannot make a single independent decision. On the contrary, the "democratic" style of management, the tradition of collegial decision-making in the institution, strongly opposes the concentration of responsibility for strategy development and implementation by the leader, even in emergency situations that require authoritarian management. management.

Nevertheless, teamwork is preferable to concentrating responsibility for strategic decisions with the head of the educational institution, because:

In order to formulate a strategy, in-depth strategic research is needed, which affects the areas of competence of different functional units. A strategic choice is best if, in its implementation, the opinions of the best experts of the institution in their functional areas are taken into account. It is necessary to ensure the distribution of responsibility for strategic decisions between them, the optimal ratio between initiative and caution, between risky measures and conservatism;

When forming a strategic management group, conditions are created to take into account the ideas of experts with different (and often conflicting) opinions, which makes it possible to reach a compromise in the formation of a strategy. This, in turn, reduces resistance to strategic changes in the educational institution and increases the effectiveness of strategy implementation;

Creating a team to formulate and implement a strategy means choosing experts who have a common strategic vision and the same understanding in the organization. tasks that use the same tools to implement strategic goals and strategic decisions, etc. A team of like-minded people has a strong synergistic effect and increases the competitive power of an educational institution.

However, collective responsibility in strategic management can be a factor of organizational weakness if the responsibility of each member of the team is not balanced with his/her powers and responsibilities. Also, if the boundaries of responsibility for specific individuals are vaguely defined, cross, or not fully inclusive, group responsibility reduces the strategic effectiveness of the organization. functional tasks strategic management groups. Therefore, in order to apply the system of group responsibility in the strategic management team, it is necessary to determine the system of delegation of authority arising from the organizational culture established in the organization.

One of the main factors for achieving the competitiveness of an educational institution is the formation and strengthening of organizational advantages. Although culture is a characteristic of each organization, in creating and strengthening the strengths of the organization, as a rule, the work is carried out according to the following logical scheme:

Step 1. It is necessary to determine which of the specialists of the institution have the necessary skills and experience and compare them with the needs of the educational institution - conduct a personnel audit. Based on the conducted

personnel audit, a decision is made aimed at expanding or deepening the individual skills of specialists to the extent necessary for the entire organization. In parallel, measures are taken to encourage the team.

Step 2. At this stage, the analysis of the results of the formation of organizational advantages is carried out, which consists of a continuous assessment and study of the level of learning of the organization to work effectively and efficiently.

Step 3. This step, as a rule, is compared with the process of forming the main activity strategies over time. From the point of view of the formation of organizational advantages, this process is complemented by the order of delegation of powers in strategically important areas of activity and the most influential positions.

Step 4. After political decisions are made about the responsibility for a specific activity, specific decisions must be made about what authority and to whom it will be given, taking into account individual and personal characteristics. business qualities. As a rule, at this stage, the current management structure is determined and the areas of responsibility of the top management of the organization are separated.

One of the important decisions made at this stage is to determine the type of management structure. At the same time, it should be remembered that the increasing democratization of management, the abandonment of authoritarianism in making management decisions increases the interest of pedagogues in effective work.

Step 5. At this step, control of relations in the organization and coordination within the company is carried out. The classic method of activity coordination is based on summarization of information flows in the management system and decision-making taking into account decisions. general condition. It should be remembered that the more formal the relations in the organization are, the more support they require, the more often the task of redistributing resources appears, the higher the probability of conflict.

Step 6. At the final stage of forming organizational advantages, decisions about the immediate environment are made. At this stage, the division of responsibility for the coordination of actions with the partners of the educational institution is carried out. The existence of stable external relations of the educational institution is an important organizational advantage, because in market

conditions, extensive relations with guarantees of multiple levels of communication, coordination and control are necessary.

When evaluating the developed strategy, a set of indicators of the external and internal environment is taken into account. During the analysis, the performance of the state task by the educational institution, the level of satisfaction of consumers with educational services, the competitiveness of the educational institution, and the increased reputation of the institution in the society are evaluated. The success of the strategy is evidenced by the balance of the educational institution's budget, teachers' attention to the introduction of innovations, the formation of the organization's value system, the absence of conflicts and other features of the social and organizational environment.

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